

POLICIES OF EDUCATIONAL JOURNALS REGARDING DEPOSIT IN REPOSITORIES

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Abstract

Collaboration among researchers is key to scientific progress, and data sharing plays a vital role in ensuring transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility. Despite existing measures, significant disparities remain in data deposition practices across academic fields. In education, there is still limited evidence regarding data sharing practices. This study analyzes the editorial policies of 60 journals from the three education categories in the Web of Science Core Collection. Results show that most journals in Education & Educational Research encourage data deposition, though few specify platforms. Sage Journals stands out for requiring data sharing, while Springer and other publishers recommend public repositories. In contrast, only six journals in Education, Scientific Disciplines have clear data-sharing policies, with some promoting specific repositories. The Education Special category reveals a more consistent approach, with 16 journals addressing data sharing. Challenges in education include managing qualitative data, insufficient infrastructure, and a lack of incentives or training. Raising awareness about the importance of raw data sharing from the outset of research is essential for improving accessibility and reproducibility. Standardizing editorial policies could simplify data sharing and foster a greater commitment to open science in education.

Keywords: Data deposition, educational research, editorial policies, data sharing, repositories.

1 INTRODUCTION

Science is a fundamental pillar in the construction of knowledge, and the communication of research findings through scientific publications is an essential element of this process [1]. Collaboration among researchers is considered a driving force behind scientific development [2], and the rise of open access, along with advances in information and communication technologies, has brought knowledge closer to society [3]. Scientific articles may be accompanied by additional materials, such as raw data and supplementary materials, which enrich their content and can be shared and reused in another research [1].

At both the international and national levels, measures are being implemented to promote data sharing in research [4;5]. Although progress has been observed, differences in data deposition persist across various fields of knowledge. For instance, in the field of education, despite the recognized importance of data for research, there is still a lack of evidence regarding data-sharing practices. A recent study found that while funding agencies have begun to require explicit data-sharing plans, the practice of data sharing in educational sciences remains relatively rare. This is partly due to the fact that many researchers are unaware of these requirements and benefits, and because data sharing is generally not part of formal training, leaving many researchers unsure of how to properly share their data. Furthermore, the research culture in educational sciences is often filled with concerns about data sharing [6].

This study aims to analyze the editorial policies of educational journals to assess their commitment to data openness, identify areas for improvement, and promote best practices in data management. The importance of this analysis lies in the fact that, by understanding editorial policies, we can identify

barriers and opportunities for data sharing, which is essential for fostering transparency, reproducibility, and accessibility in educational research.

2 METHODOLOGY

The editorial policies of 60 education journals were analyzed regarding the deposition of data accompanying published articles in repositories. For this, the author guidelines of the top five education journals in each quartile of the three subject categories of Education in the Web of Science were examined: Education, Scientific Disciplines (SCIE), Education & Educational Research (SSCI), and Education, Special (SSCI). The selection of these journals was based on their ranking within the Web of Science quartiles, as this database provides a comprehensive and internationally recognized representation of scientific publications. This approach allowed us to obtain a representative and balanced sample of the editorial landscape in education, ensuring that both prestigious journals and those representing a wide range of subdisciplines within the field of education were included. Moreover, focusing on editorial policies is crucial because these policies establish the expectations and guidelines for authors regarding data sharing. Understanding these policies enables us to identify specific barriers and opportunities that affect data-sharing practices in the field of education.

3 RESULTS

Figure 1 provides data on the policies of the selected journals regarding supplementary materials (whether they allow the submission of additional materials that complement the main research article), data acceptance (whether they accept and/or encourage the submission of raw research data accompanying the article), data reuse (whether they promote the reuse of research data by other researchers), and deposition practices (whether they require or recommend that research data be deposited in thematic or institutional repositories for public access) in the three subject categories of educational journals of the Web of Science.

It is shown that subject categories Education and Educational Research and Education, Special have the highest rates of acceptance for supplementary materials and data, with 17 and 19 journals, respectively. However, data reuse is less common, particularly in the subject categories Education and Educational Research (7 journals) and Education, Scientific Disciplines (5 journals), with a noticeable prominence in Education, Special.

It is observed that Education, Special stands out in all the items chosen to evaluate data policies in the journals, while Education, Scientific Disciplines hosts the fewest journals that promote the practice, notably scoring lower across all items. Additionally, it is noteworthy that very few journals provide information for the author about publication on their own website or an institutional page.

Figure 1. Journals' policies about data and supplementary material (education subject categories)

Figure 2 considers data distribution by quartiles, as it was intended to check whether there was any difference in data policies directly related to the journal's quartile position. It is noteworthy that Q1 journals have a higher number of data policies per journal across all items, except for reuse, which remains at the lowest level (5 journals), along with Q4 journals. Similarly, it is striking that Q3 journals contain more explicit data-sharing policies across all items compared to Q2, and that Q4 journals stand out with a large number of policies regarding the acceptance of supplementary material, surpassing both Q2 and Q3.

Figure 2. Journals' policies about data and supplementary material (quartiles)

If regarding publishers, 16 out of 20 journals examined in the subject category Education and Educational Research promote the deposition of data in repositories without specifying particular

platforms. Some publishers, such as Elsevier, maintain partnerships with specific repositories like ScienceDirect. Notably, Sage Journals has adopted a policy that requires authors to share their research data or provide a detailed explanation if sharing is not possible. Meanwhile, Springer recommends depositing data in public repositories and suggests a list of recommended platforms. Both Wiley and Taylor & Francis emphasize the importance of depositing data in public repositories but do not specify any particular ones.

In contrast, only 6 out of 20 journals in the area of Education, Scientific Disciplines have specific policies regarding data deposition. Wiley is involved in two of these journals. Among them, the European Journal of Dental Education stands out as it specifically mandates that research data deposits must comply with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles for research data. Taylor & Francis and Springer are also present in this category with varying deposition policies, though without naming any specific repositories. Ubiquity Press, for its part, requires the submission of research data and the preparation of a report guiding readers on how to access the data.

In the category of Education, Special, 16 out of 20 journals address data deposition in their editorial policies. Sage Journals, with 9 journals in this category, deposits data in Figshare, with the exception of videos and podcasts. Elsevier, with 2 journals, collaborates with ScienceDirect repositories for data storage. Springer, with one journal in this category, suggests the use of general repositories such as Dryad or Figshare. Taylor & Francis, with 4 journals, requires the publication of supplementary material in Figshare and data in ScholeXplorer in three of them, while in the remaining journal, data deposition in public repositories is mentioned.

Lastly, it is worth noting that out of the 60 journals analyzed, 52 were edited by commercial publishers, 6 by associations, 1 was independent, and 1 belonged to a university. These last two samples had no policies regarding the use of data in their digital versions, except for the university publisher, which explicitly stated that it did not allow the acceptance of supplementary material.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The growing trend towards data deposition in educational journals marks significant progress towards transparency and accessibility in scientific research [7]. However, data deposition policies vary in terms of the specificity of the recommended repository and other particulars, such as the field of study [3]. For example, in the subject category Education and Educational Sciences, there is a greater emphasis on promoting data deposition in repositories without specifying particular platforms, although some publishers like Elsevier and Sage Journals are associated with specific repositories or require authors to share their data. On the other hand, in Education, Scientific Disciplines, although fewer journals have deposition policies, one stands out for specifically mentioning the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). Meanwhile, in Education, Special, most journals address data deposition and present a wider variety of repositories.

This variability in policies reflects differences in research practices and data management across various educational fields. In particular, researchers in education often work with qualitative data, which can be more challenging to share than the quantitative data typical of other disciplines. Additionally, the infrastructure and incentives for data sharing remain insufficient in many educational contexts [6].

The disparity in data deposition policies across different fields of education highlights the need for greater standardization and clarity to promote effective data management practices in this area. The lack of instruction in data-sharing practices and the uncertainties this generates among researchers may be contributing to the low frequency of data exchange in education [6].

Overall, it can be concluded that raising scientists' awareness of the importance of data sharing from the start of their research is crucial, promoting the deposition of raw data as an essential practice. This will facilitate access to science, enhance its reproducibility, and save time and resources, in line with the FAIR principles [6]. Reviewing and unifying editorial policies across journals could simplify the process of collectively sharing data [8]. Focusing on the field of education, it is clear that the scientific community dedicated to this area should be more committed to data sharing, as education is a driver of change and a fundamental right of society.

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INTRODUCTION

Science plays a fundamental role in knowledge creation, and the dissemination of research findings through publications is essential [1]. Collaboration among researchers is a driving force behind scientific progress, and open access has brought knowledge closer to society [2,3]. Scientific publications often include supplementary materials, such as raw data, which can be shared and reused [1]. Both international and national efforts have been made to promote data sharing, yet discrepancies in data deposition practices persist across disciplines. In education, despite the recognized importance of data, data sharing remains rare. This is partly due to a lack of awareness about the requirements and benefits, as well as insufficient formal training. Moreover, concerns within the research culture of educational sciences hinder data sharing [4]. This study aims to examine the editorial policies of educational journals to evaluate their commitment to data openness, identify areas for improvement, and promote best practices in data management.

METHODOLOGY

The editorial policies of 60 education journals were analyzed regarding data deposition practices. The top five journals from each quartile in three Web of Science categories—Education Scientific Disciplines (SCIE), Education & Educational Research (SSCI), and Education Special (SSCI)—were selected. This selection ensured a representative and balanced sample of journals from diverse subfields. Examining author guidelines provided insights into expectations for data sharing, allowing for the identification of barriers and opportunities in educational data-sharing practices.

RESULTS

Education & Educational Research and Education Special categories have the highest rates of acceptance for supplementary materials and data (17 and 19 journals, respectively). However, data reuse is less common, particularly in Education & Educational Research (7 journals) and Education Scientific Disciplines (5 journals). Education Special excels in all evaluated data policies, while Education Scientific Disciplines has the fewest journals promoting these practices. Notably, few journals provide publication information on their own or institutional websites (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Journals' policies about data and supplementary material (education subject categories)

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Q1 journals have the most data policies across all items, except for data reuse, which is lowest in both Q1 and Q4 (5 journals). Q3 journals have more explicit data-sharing policies than Q2, while Q4 journals excel in the acceptance of supplementary materials, surpassing Q2 and Q3 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Journals' policies about data and supplementary material (quartiles)

Of the 20 journals in Education & Educational Research, 16 promote data deposition in repositories, though most do not specify platforms. Elsevier partners with repositories like ScienceDirect, while Sage Journals requires data sharing or justification for not sharing. Springer recommends public repositories, and Wiley and Taylor & Francis emphasize data deposition without specifying platforms. In Education Scientific Disciplines, only 6 out of 20 journals have data deposition policies, with Wiley and the European Journal of Dental Education mandating compliance with FAIR principles. In Education Special, 16 out of 20 journals address data deposition, with Sage, Elsevier, and Springer recommending repositories like Figshare. Lastly, 52 of the 60 journals are edited by commercial publishers, while 8 are from associations, universities, or are independent.

CONCLUSION

The increasing trend of data deposition in educational journals promotes transparency and accessibility in research, but policies vary widely by field. Education & Educational Sciences emphasizes data deposition without specifying repositories, while Education Scientific Disciplines highlights FAIR principles. Education Special includes a broader range of repositories. These differences point to challenges in sharing qualitative data and insufficient infrastructure. Standardizing data-sharing policies and improving researcher training are key to promoting data exchange, enhancing reproducibility, and aligning with FAIR principles